

CUSP thematic workshop series Human Risk Assessment of MNPs

Register here: https://bit.ly/CUSP_WS3_Registration

Workshop #3/3

Practice-based analysis of data needs, availability, reuse and gaps for MNP-risk related tools

Friday 21st April 2023, 09:00-13:30 CEST

Preliminary Agenda

09:00 Welcome and summary of previous workshops from a data needs perspective
Rudolf Reuther and Bernd Giese, PlasticsFatE

I. Types of data needed for tools related to risk of MNP in CUSP and beyond

09:15 With input from:
POLYRISK: Andrea Haase
PlasticHeal: Steffen Foss Hansen
IMPTOX: Ivana Banic
PlasticsFatE: Dana Kühnel
PAPILLONS: Luca Nizetto

10:30 Coffee break

10:45 Preliminary summary on data needs
Christina Hipfinger, PlasticsFatE
Structured discussion about key requirements in terms of data

12:00 Coffee break

II. Data sources and data processing for risk related tools

12:10 Study quality assessment approach
Anita Jemec Kokalj,
University of Ljubljana

12:25 Introduction to data sources /eNanoMapper, types and definitions of data
Nina Jeliaskova, IDEAconsult Ltd

12:40 Conclusion and future steps

During the workshop we will invite you to answer four questions using mentimeter.

Go to www.menti.com
enter code **1834 6371**

Or

Use the QR code →

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CUSP Workshop III:

Practice-based analysis of data needs, availability, reuse and gaps for MNP-risk related tools

April 21, 2023, 09:00 - 13:30 CEST

Background information

An analysis of the risk associated with micro and nanoplastics (MNP) includes a number of aspects that should be considered. In addition to information about the material itself, its applications and its life cycle, it is necessary to analyze the hazard and exposure to enable a risk characterization. Different methods can be used for each part of the risk assessment process. For example, Integrated Approaches for Testing and Assessment (IATAs) for hazard assessment or Material Flow Analysis (MFA) to provide a basis for calculating Predicted Environmental Concentrations (PECs) to estimate exposure. A number of methods are being applied or newly developed in ongoing projects aimed at improving our understanding of the health effects of MNPs. Depending on which part of the risk assessment they belong to, they may require different kinds of input information, as exemplified in the following figure:

In this rather practice based workshop we will address the necessary input information and data types of the different methods for characterizing MNP risks and discuss the problems associated with them.

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To this end, contributions from the CUSP projects and the EU project PAPILLONS on plastic in agricultural production will first provide an overview of their approaches along the following questions:

1. what methods are you developing (or applying) for risk analysis/risk assessment?
2. what type of data do you need?
3. are there any problems in collecting these data?
4. what sources do you use to obtain the data?

In a structured discussion, we will try to determine if the methods are compatible with the available data or if there are gaps or even problems with the format or quality of the data. A second part of the discussion will be devoted to ideas on how to solve the problems identified.

Sometimes the data exist somewhere but are hard to find, not harmonized, and not centralized in a common database. In addition, the quality of the studies in which the data were generated also plays a role. These issues will be addressed in two presentations in the second part of the workshop. In a final discussion we want to concretize the further steps, taking into account the input from the second part of the workshop.